

Supplementary information

Mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction

Mateja Knap^{1,2}, Urška Lavrenčič Štangar², Andrijana Sever Škapin^{1,3}, Miroslava Filip Edelmannová⁴, Kamila Kočí⁴, Peter Nadrah^{1,*}

¹ Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute, Dimičeva ulica 12, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

² University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Večna pot 113, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

³ Faculty of Polymer Technology, Ozare 19, 2380 Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

⁴ Institute of Environmental Technology, CEET, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava-Poruba 708 00, Czech Republic

Diffractograms

Figure S1. Diffractograms of the synthesized TiO₂-CeO₂ composites. The curves are offset on the y-axis.

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy

Figure S2. Normalized Kubelka-Munk transformations of the reflectance spectra for TCO samples and CeO₂ calcined once (label CeO₂*). The curves are offset by 0.1 value.

Figure S3. Normalized Kubelka-Munk transformations of the reflectance spectra for PM samples and CeO₂ calcined twice (label CeO₂**). The curves are offset by 0.1 value.

Photographs of the materials

Figure S4. Photographs of the materials. * and ** refers to material thermally treated once and twice, respectively.